

BALANCING THE RIGHTS OF ACCUSED, VICTIM AND SOCIETY- STRAY THOUGHTS FROM THE CONVICTION RATES FOR VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN AND GIRL CRIMES

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Abstract

Violence prove or feel a sense of power. It can be perpetrated by those in power against the powerless, or by the powerless in retaliation which attempts to deny their powerlessness. Any hierarchical social system has an in-built gradation of domination and subordination, as well as institutionalized violence and victimization. This is perpetuated by various means — subtle pressure through the power of ideology, the mechanism of internalized social norms, and the system of social sanctions which penalizes non-compliance. Often the threat of violence is enough for exerting power, while sometimes an atmosphere of terror is created towards the same end. This paper is an attempt to analyse the violent crime in India and control system.

Key Words: violent crimes, imprisonment, Accused, Victim and Society.

Introduction:

There are forms of violence which are directed specifically against women ~ rape, sexual harassment, sexual exploitation as in prostitution, sexual debasement as in pornography,

domestic violence ranging from battery to torture and even death. All these spring from the structure of patriarchy, defined broadly as a system of male dominance legitimated within the family and society through superior rights, privileges, authority and power. The degree and forms of expression of patriarchy vary from society to society. But the process of subordination is generally achieved by devaluing women's contribution, while at the same time extracting a significant contribution from them. A second process occurs through a powerful ideology of rigidly assigned roles for women, which act as boundaries for all their actions — boundaries which can be overstepped at their own peril. The most potent and restrictive injunction is the virtual debarment of women in public places or places typically designated as the male sphere. Further, sexual morality has double standards for men and women, the latter being subjected to strict norms.

Finally, they underscore the inadequacy, ineffectiveness and unwillingness of the State machinery to curb violence against women. Violence against women, then, has to be seen in the context of the Indian society in transition which has committed itself to the values of equality and justice, but which is unable to make the dominant socio-economic segments and the male population relinquish their traditionally held rights and power over the weaker segments and women. In many spheres of life, such as marriage customs, occupations, norms of everyday social behaviour, there is a cultural lag, and even a backlash when the hitherto powerless groups seek to demand their newly available rights. Violence thus becomes both a symptom and a cause of social tensions. Secondly, the question as to whether violence against women is really increasing, or whether a false impression of greater incidence is created because it is being reported to a greater degree than before, is a debatable one.

There is reason to believe that there is an increase in both incidence and reporting. The increased incidence can be inferred from the fact that some types of violent crimes are relatively new, as for example the burning of brides for not fulfilling of exorbitant dowry demands, and the use of the new clinical sex selection tests for female foeticide. At the same time, it must be emphasized that in spite of increased reporting and awareness, the proportion of reported crimes to total crimes remains very low. This is true of crimes such as rape or forced prostitution which stigmatize the victim, as also of domestic violence which is considered to be an internal family

affair and a matter of family honour. The general tendency of women, thus, is to avoid reporting incidents of violence against them; in addition, pressure is often brought upon them to remain quiet

REALITES.

On 13 September 2013, a New Delhi judge sentenced four men to death for the brutal gang rape of a 23-year-old physiotherapy student. She died due to severe injuries suffered during the attack. The barbaric nature of the crime appalled the country and brought worldwide attention to what print media now calls the Rape crisis of India . Nationwide protests forced lawmakers to refer this case to a fast-track court, and the judgment was pronounced in less than a year. The perpetrators were sentenced to the gallows, a punishment reserved in Indian law for the *rarest of the rare* instances of inhuman crime. The government sought to appease the widespread street protests in many cities. The law concerning violence against women was amended by the Parliament .The maximum punishment for rape resulting in death (or vegetative state) of the victim was modified from life imprisonment to include death penalty. Other laws related to sexual crime were made stricter, in the hope that this would deter people from committing such crimes.

The numbers of violent crimes in India especially those against women including rape that are reported in official statistics are increasing with each passing year . This violence thrives within a milieu of steady economic growth, and increasing inequality between the rich and poor in Indian society; India's GINI coefficient that has increased from 0.32 to 0.38 in the last two decades is evidence to that .India's new riches and development strides as witnessed by its GDP growth from \$450.42 billion in 2000 to \$1841.7 billion seem to bear no fruits for its women. In 2012, the crimes against women reported by official statistics increased by 24.7%, compared to those reported in 2008 . Ranging from the so-called *eve teasing* and outright sexual harassment on the street or workplace, to harassment for *dowry*, molestation in public transport vehicles, and the often-reported rape, these crimes against women reflect the vulnerability and deep-rooted problems related to the position of women in Indian society. Out of 28 states, 10 states reported

more than 10,000 cases of crime against women in 2011 putting states with both high and low HDI (Human Development Index) and literacy rates in the list; probably an indication that education and economic growth alone do not influence the occurrence of these crimes and pointing towards socio-political and cultural factors. This can be further observed in the National Crime Records Bureau (NRCB) statistics which show that cruelty by a husband or his relatives (46.8%) and *dowry*-related crimes (7.1%) account for more than half of the crimes against women. With increased incidence and visibility of these gruesome crimes, there is an urgent need to address this problem at multiple levels of Indian society, including professional, familial and social settings. According to the NCRB, 24,923 cases of rape were reported in 2012 , amounting to one rape every 22 minutes.

A continuous increase in the reported cases of rape has been observed in the period from 2009 to 2012 with more than 3% increase in the number of cases reported in 2012 over 2011. Nearly, 12.5% (3,125) of the total victims of rape were girls younger than 14 years, 23.9% (5,957) were in the 14–18 age group, 50.2% (12,511) were in the 18–30 age group and 12.8% (3,187 victims) were in the 30–50 age group. These statistics possibly do not capture the actual numbers. While gross under-reporting could be one reason for this the other reason is that crimes such as gang rapes, stalking and acid attacks on women were not included in official statistics of crime against women until the law was amended on 3 February 2013 . Even amongst those crimes, the NCRB statistics takes only the principal offence of the formal complaint (First Information Report) into account. So in cases such as the Delhi gang rape, which resulted in the death of the rape victim, the rape would be unaccounted for in the official statistics; the true scale of gender violence thus remaining undercounted.

The problem of underestimation of the gender-based crime is compounded by failure of the justice system of the country in securing convictions. The NCRB statistics show that 54.6% of rape cases reported in 2011 are yet to be investigated, while 30.6% are waiting for trial. Only 16% of the cases have resulted in convictions. The recent protests demanded for stricter laws, possibly under an assumption that greater punishment will reduce the rate of sexual crime.

However, with the abysmal conviction rate, stricter laws alone may not achieve the necessary deterrence.

The NCRB data for 2013 also shows the same trend .There is a spike in registration of crimes against women even as murders have dropped by 3.6%.Besides rapes, there is a 56% increase in crimes described as outraging the modesty of women, involving assault, anda 37% rise in the offence of insult to women. Delhi leads the pack with a 340% rise in crimes against women. Next is Mumbai, which recorded a jump of around 80%-90% .Chennai proving to be the exception recorded a negative growth in the category.

Conviction rates- An analysis

In 1953 the authors of India’s first ever crime survey presented a grim picture of the state of the new country’s police forces. There has been no improvement in the methods of investigation or in the application of science to investigation. From the various years National Crime Record Bureau’s statistical database it is evident that there are more and more women approaching police with complaints of offences pertaining to rape and sexual offences, forced marriage, honour based violence ,child abuse, human trafficking, with a focus on trafficking for sexual exploitation, prostitution ,pornography, stalking and harassment, Domestic Violence and the like . We also gather from the NCRB that even more and more women approach police with complaints, ever fewer victims gets justice. For example according to the Bureau’s reports on crime in India, 27.2% of all rape cases tried in court in 2006 ended with convictions. In 2013, it was 27.1%.

Number of cases of rape reported across India

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Data: National Crime Records Bureau

Percentage of rape cases resulting in conviction

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Data: National Crime Records Bureau

Criminal Justice System consists of seven vital components, namely, criminal law, police, prosecution, judiciary, correctional institutions, administration and societal culture and ethos. Improvement is needed in all these sectors which are mutually exclusive. However, police and judiciary are front line segments. Any improvement in the system and sensitivity of these components would certainly make a dent on crime against women.

Conclusion:

The abysmally low conviction rates for crimes against women is worrisome. Hence it is important to build the capacity of the police force to deal effectively and sensitively with matters related to crime against women. This requires a change in the mindset of the police force. In this regard, measures that can be followed are organising sensitivity training of the police. Further, the police forces, on a continuous and regular basis, should be educated about the rights of women. The investigative and forensic ability of the law enforcement agencies also needs to be augmented. Modern investigative techniques need to be replacing the archaic police and investigating manuals that are still being followed.

Apart from implementing police reforms, we also need to ensure that there are adequate number of judges to hear the rape cases and other cases involving crime against women. Thus, the need is to augment the number of judges to make sure that justice is delivered in a prompt manner. We are in dire need of fast track courts to ensure speedy justice in rape and cases of sexual harassment and domestic violence. We also need a time-bound action plan by states to deal with pending cases of crimes against women.